

IMAGE OF THE MONTH

A child without kneecaps**Question**

A 5-year-old boy was referred to the orthopaedic department for genu valgum. During the physical examination, kneecaps could not be seen or palpated bilaterally (Fig. 1). No other clinical abnormalities were found, except for the presence of hypoplastic nails on both thumbs (Fig. 2). In the suspect of nail-patella syndrome (NPS), a pelvic X-ray was performed (Fig. 3). What is the typical finding associated with this condition? (Answer on page ••)

Fig. 1 Patient's knees with non-palpable kneecaps.

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Fig. 2 Hypoplastic thumbnail.

Fig. 3 Iliac horns on pelvic X-ray.

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Answer

The X-ray shows the presence of iliac horns. Iliac horns are bilateral, conical bony processes that project posteriorly and laterally from the central part of the iliac bones of the pelvis. Their presence is highly suggestive of NPS.

NPS is a rare genetic condition characterised by hypoplastic or absent kneecaps, nails' abnormalities and altered mobility of the elbows.¹ Up to 50% of the patients develop renal involvement that usually presents with proteinuria, whether isolated or associated with haematuria.^{2,3} Proteinuria can be self-limiting and spontaneously remit, or it can evolve to nephrotic syndrome, so that around 10% of the patients develop end-stage renal disease.⁴ Eyes might be involved as well. In fact, ocular hypertension and primary open angle glaucoma occur at higher rates compared to the general population.⁵

Our patient's urinary dipstick tested negative and his eye examination resulted normal.

Genetic analyses investigated for pathogenic variants of *LMX1B* (NM_002316), the only gene responsible for the disease. In our patient, we detected a novel *de novo* *LMX1B* mutation (c.242delT; pLeu81Cysfs*84). The mutation is classified as pathogenic according the ACMG guidelines, and it is predicted to result in nonsense mediated decay.

The prognosis of NPS is usually good but strictly dependent on the degree of renal involvement. In case of proteinuria, ACE inhibitors should be started immediately to slow down the

progression of the disease. Periodic follow-up includes annual blood pressure measurement, urinary dipstick and ocular tonometry. Due to the instability of its extensor portion, a surgical management of the knee is often required already in childhood.⁶

Written consent was obtained for the publication of potentially identifying images and clinical details.

References

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